

Physical Properties of Fatty Acid Esters of 1,2-Propane Diol. Part-II : Diacid Diesters from Odd Chain Fatty Acids*

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Several diacid diesters of 1,2-propane diol having either palmitic, stearic or nonadecanoic acids in 1-position and different fatty acids in 2-position were synthesised for the first time. Melting point of solid esters, and density, refractive index and viscosity of all esters in liquid state at different temperatures are reported and discussed. Alternation of m.p. occurs in all the three 1,2-propane diol-diacid diester series.

ALTERNATION of melting points was observed¹ for 1-monoesters and monoacid diesters of 1,2-propane diol (pg). The properties of mixed acid diesters are now reported.

Experimental

The fatty acids used in this study are the same as those used in the earlier one¹.

TLC-pure 1-monopalmitate, 1-monostearate and 1-monononadecanoate of pg were prepared as described earlier² and the hydroxyl group at the 2-position was esterified with appropriate acid chloride in the case of long chain fatty acids and acid anhydrides in the case of short chain fatty acids. Methods used for purifying the diesters and determination of their properties were essentially the same as described earlier¹⁻⁴.

Results and Discussion

Properties of diacid diesters having palmitic or stearic acid at 1-position of pg are given in Table 1,

and of those having nonadecanoic acid are given in Table 2. The m.p. of the highest melting form was

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF DIACID DIESTERS OF PG HAVING NONADECANOIC ACID IN 1-POSITION

Fatty acid in 2-position of diester	m.p. (β-Form) °C	Density at 80° g/ml	Ref. Index n _D ²⁰	Viscosity at 80° cps
Odd chain fatty acids				
Propionic	—	0.8656	1.4225	3.92
Valeric	—	0.8615	1.4250	3.95
Heptanoic	—	0.8585	1.4267	4.12
Nonanoic	—	0.8553	1.4286	4.60
Undecanoic	—	0.8525	1.4297	5.15
Tridecanoic	37.1	0.8507	1.4305	5.81
Pentadecanoic	42.5	0.8492	1.4318	6.29
Heptadecanoic	46.3	0.8478	1.4329	6.99
Even chain fatty acids				
Acetic	—	0.8670	1.4212	4.00
Butyric	—	0.8637	1.4238	3.92
Caproic	—	0.8601	1.4258	4.02
Caprylic	—	0.8571	1.4274	4.39
Capric	—	0.8545	1.4291	4.89
Lauric	38.9	0.8518	1.4302	5.50
Myristic	43.7	0.8501	1.4311	6.02
Palmitic	47.2	0.8486	1.4323	6.69
Stearic	50.4	0.8477	1.4335	7.51

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF DIACID DIESTERS OF PG HAVING EITHER STEARIC OR PALMITIC ACID IN 1-POSITION

Fatty acid in 2-position of diester	m.p. (β-Form) °C	Density at 80° g/ml	Ref. Index n _D ²⁰	Viscosity at 80° cps
1-Monostearate derivatives				
Propionic	—	0.8670	1.4218	3.72
Valeric	—	0.8633	1.4238	3.77
Heptanoic	—	0.8597	1.4259	4.09
Nonanoic	—	0.8570	1.4275	4.42
Undecanoic	—	0.8543	1.4290	4.97
Tridecanoic	38.2	0.8517	1.4299	5.60
Pentadecanoic	46.0	0.8498	1.4311	6.18
Heptadecanoic	49.4	0.8484	1.4324	6.69
Nonadecanoic	50.2	0.8472	1.4335	7.34
1-Monopalmitate derivatives				
Pentadecanoic	37.1	0.8517	1.4298	5.30
Heptadecanoic	42.3	0.8502	1.4310	5.95
Nonadecanoic	47.0	0.8485	1.4323	6.56

determined. Even though the physical properties of the diesters in liquid state were measured at 10° intervals (from 40-80°), only the values at 80° are being reported. The relationship between m.p. and the number of carbon atoms in the fatty acid present at 2-position of the diesters is shown in Fig. 1, and that for density, refractive index and viscosity is shown in Figs. 2, 3 and 4, respectively.

In the three series of diesters (having either palmitic, stearic or nonadecanoic acid in 1-position and varying acyl chain at 2-position), m.p., refractive index and viscosity increases with the increase in the length of the acyl chain at the 2-position whilst density decreases.

There is a clear indication of alternation of m.p. (Fig. 1) in all the diacid diester series, as was found⁴

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for the 1-monoesters and monoacid diesters. This is, no doubt, due to the effect of the nature of acyl chain (whether odd or even) on the mode of molecular packing in solid state, which is further accentuated by the presence of the methyl group at 2-position of pg, unlike for other normal fatty acid esters.

Fig. 1. Melting behaviour of diesters of pg having: (A) palmitic and stearic acids and (B) nonadecanoic acid in 1-position (solid points are earlier reported values²).

Fig. 2. Relationship of density and number of carbon atoms in the fatty acid at 2-position of 1-monononadecanoate at different temperatures.

Fig. 3. Relationship of refractive index and number of carbon atoms in the fatty acid at 2-position of 1-monononadecanoate at different temperatures.

Fig. 4. Relationship of viscosity and number of carbon atoms in the fatty acid at 2-position of 1-monononadecanoate at different temperatures.

As expected for any homologous series, if the odd and even chain fatty acid esters are segregated into two series, the differences in m.p. of adjacent members reduce as the series is ascended, as can be calculated from data in Tables 1 and 2, and clearly seen from the shape of curves in Fig. 1.

Irrespective of the nature of the acyl chain (whether odd or even chain) present in pg esters, the density decreases and the refractive index increases with the molecular weight of the compound, but the differences between adjacent members in a series are slightly more for the lower molecular weight esters than for the higher ones. Unlike for m.p., the relationship between density or refractive index and the number of carbon atoms in the acyl chain at the 2-position can be represented by a single curve (Figs. 2 and 3). Similar trends exist for the diacid diesters having palmitic or stearic acid at the 1-position (graphs not reproduced). For all the diacid diester series studied, density and refractive index changes are linear with temperature; their average temperature coefficients are -6.93×10^{-4} and -3.98×10^{-4} . These values compare well with those reported earlier for monoacid diesters of odd chain fatty acids¹ (-7.01×10^{-4} ; -3.99×10^{-4}) and for even chain fatty acids² (-6.98×10^{-4} ; -3.97×10^{-4}).

The viscosity increases with increasing molecular weight for the compounds in all the three series, except that the diacid diester having propionic acid in 2-position has a lower viscosity than the one with acetic acid. It appears that with short chain esters, strong polar forces exert some influence on the flow properties, which then subsequently subside perceptibly as molecular weight increases beyond those of propionic acid derivatives, when other lateral forces between the methylene groups of the acyl chain gains preponderance. The viscosity decreases with increase in temperature and

these decreases are non linear. In all the cases, however, log viscosity has a linear relationship with reciprocal of absolute temperature.

Data on the properties of some pg esters, having the same molecular weight are given in Table 3.

Fatty acid		m.p. °C	Properties in liquid state at 60°		
at 1-position	at 2-position		Density g/ml	n _D	Viscosity cps
Nonadecanoic	Stearic	50.4	0.8614	1.4414	12.38
Stearic	Nonadecanoic	50.2	0.8608	1.4412	12.18
Nonadecanoic	Palmitic	47.2	0.8623	1.4402	10.95
Palmitic	Nonadecanoic	47.0	0.8622	1.4401	10.91
Heptadecanoic	Nonadecanoic	45.7	0.8615	1.4410	11.29
Nonadecanoic	Heptadecanoic	46.3	0.8616	1.4408	11.55
Heptadecanoic	Palmitic	42.5	0.8637	1.4390	9.89
Palmitic	Heptadecanoic	42.3	0.8638	1.4390	9.78

The four pairs of positionally isomeric diesters (same molecular weight) have the same density and refractive index, but they differ slightly in their m.ps. and viscosities. The differences in the m.ps. of isomeric diesters having one odd and one even

chain fatty acid is very small (0.2°), but the difference increases when both the acids are odd. Similar observations were made for pg diesters having even chain acids at both the positions. It was reported⁹ that amongst the isomeric pairs the one having a longer chain at 1-position has a higher m.p. and viscosity, in liquid state, at any given temperature, even though their refractive indices and densities are identical. Whilst confirming these observations, the present study clearly shows that the nature of the acyl chain (whether odd or even) arising out of increments of the carbon atoms, and their relative positions on the pg moiety has an influence on the intermolecular attraction forces in both solid and liquid states.

References

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